

Scheme II

The rate of formation of the complex is zero at steady state and hence the concentration of complex

$$[X] = \frac{k_4[S][\text{Os(VIII)}]}{k_{-4} + k_5[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

The rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate (III) is

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_4k_5[S][\text{Os(VIII)}][\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-4} + k_5[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

$$1/\left(-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt}\right) = \frac{k_{-4}}{2k_4k_5[S][\text{Os(VIII)}][\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{1}{2k_4[S][\text{Os(VIII)}]} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

A plot $\frac{1}{\text{reaction velocity}}$ vs. $\frac{1}{[\text{OH}^-]}$ should give a straight line with a positive intercept at the Y-axis. Such a plot is shown in Figure 1 which justifies the validity of the rate equation (11). The observed stoichiometry of 6.5 can be explained by considering that steps (i) and (ii) take place to the extent of 80% and 20% respectively. (i) $\text{PhCH}_2\text{COCOO}^- + 6\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-} + 5\text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{PhCHO} + 2\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (ii) $\text{PhCH}_2\text{COCOO}^- + 8\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-} + 8\text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{PhCOO}^- + 2\text{CO}_2 + 8\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} + 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The possibility that enolization of β -phenyl pyruvate followed by the oxidation and subsequent rupture of C-C bond to give initially benzaldehyde and oxalic acid, cannot be totally ruled out. However, it has earlier been shown⁹ that oxalic acid is not completely oxidized to CO_2 under the condition at which the reaction is carried out. The absence of oxalic acid in the reaction mixture indicates that oxidation via enolization may not take place.

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Chemical Investigation of *Poeciloneuron indicum* Leaves

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POECLONEURON INDICUM Bedd. (N. O. Guttiferae), trade name *Ballagi* is a large tree found in Western Ghats from North Kanara to Travancore at an altitude of 300–1,200 m. The tree yields a good quality timber for heavy constructional work. The fruit, bark and root of the plant are reported^{2,3} to yield friedelin. As a long range programme of better utilization of plant resources, investigation with the leaves of *P. indicum* collected from Shimoga forests (Mysore state), has been carried out and the results recorded here.

The alcoholic extractive of the shade dried powdered leaves (2 kg) was successively extracted with *n*-hexane and ether. The hexane extract on keeping deposited an FeCl_3 positive dirty yellow powder (9 g) which on crystallisation (pyridine) furnished yellowish crystals, m.p. >350° (Found: C, 55.70; H, 2.82, Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_6\text{O}_8$: C, 55.62; H, 1.98%) and was identified as *ellagic acid* by positive Griesmeyer Reichelsche reaction, and direct Comparison (TLC, IR) with an authentic sample.

The dark green residue obtained from the filtrate of ellagic acid on subsequent purification was chromatographed over Al_2O_3 column.

The *n*-hexane eluents yielded a substance, m.p. 71° (80 mg) which was identified as *hentriacontane* (m. p.; IR).

The *n*-hexane-benzene (3:1) elution of the column gave an LB positive and TNM negative residue (1.2 g) which on repeated crystallisation from benzene furnished needles, m.p. 256–258°; $(\alpha)_D^{25}$ – 30°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1709 cm^{-1} . It was identified (m.m.p., IR, TLC) as *friedelin* (Found: C, 84.45; H, 12.10. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.50; H, 11.70%).

The *n*-hexane-benzene (1 : 1) elution gave another LB positive and TNM negative residue which on crystallisation from benzene gave needles (700 mg), m.p. 286-288°; $(\alpha)_D^{25} + 29^\circ$; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3484 cm^{-1} (OH), and was identified (acetate, m.p. 293-295°) as *friedelan-3 β -ol*, (m.m.p. TLC, IR). The mother liquor yielded a waxy product (200 mg) which on purification melted at 85-86°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3298 (OH), 1459 (CH_2), 732, 722 ($-(\text{CH}_2)_n-$) cm^{-1} and was identified as *hentriacontanol* (lit m.p. 84-85°).

The ethereal extract of the alcoholic extractive (*vide supra*) gave an FeCl_3 positive (royal blue ink colour) dark green sticky product which on purification through chromatography (silica gel) and crystallisation (benzene) gave a TLC pure compound (2.5 g) as silky threads, m.p. 145-146°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3333 (OH); 1701, 1250 (ester) cm^{-1} (Found: C, 55.45; H, 5.25. Calcd. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_8$: C, 54.54; H, 5.05%). It was characterised as *ethyl gallate* (lit. m.p. 141°) by MS peaks at m/e 198 (M^+), 170 (gallic acid fragment) and triacetate, m.p. 168° (lit 170°). It could however, be an artefact of gallic acid which is presumably esterified during alcohol extraction of the plant material.

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Ethyl-N-methylallophanate, a side Product of Reactions in Ethanol with Diazomethane Solution Prepared from Nitrosomethylurea

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WE reported¹ the isolation of compound A, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8$, m.p. 134° from the acidic fractions of the chloroform extract of the leaves of *Carissa carandas* Linn. It was obtained in the chloroform eluate when the ethanolic mother liquor

of ursolic acid was treated with diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea in the standard method² and the product was chromatographed over neutral alumina. It has now been established as ethyl-N-methylallophanate (I).

Compound A exhibited a weak UV maximum (ethanol) at 275 nm (ϵ 27.3) and principal IR (nujol) bands at 3275, 1750, 1657, 1205, 1155 and 1048 cm^{-1} . The NMR in CDCl_3 showed signals at δ 1.30 (3H, *t*, $J=7$ Hz, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.2 (2H, *q*, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.90 (3H, *d*, $J=4.5$ Hz, CH_3NHCO) and 7.70 ppm (2H, *b*, 2NHCO). Its mass spectrum lacked the molecular ion and showed the most intense peak at m/e 145 ($\text{M}-1$ ion) and other principal peaks at m/e 62, 58 and 45 (scheme).

The structure was finally confirmed through its synthesis by condensation of ethylchloroformate with methylurea³ as also by the action of diazomethane on ethylallophanate.

It is thus envisaged that I is formed by the action of methylisocyanate, a contaminant in the preparation of diazomethane recently shown⁴ to lead to undesirable side products, on ethylcarbamate (II) or less likely by N-methylation⁵ of ethylallophanate (III) by diazomethane itself (Scheme). Alcoholic decomposition of nitrosomethylurea has been reported⁶ to give III apparently by the self condensation of II initially formed by the interaction of alcohol with cyanic acid⁷.

Preparation of Ethyl-N-methylallophanate (I)

(i) From methyl urea :

Methylurea (3 g) prepared according to Davis and Blanchard⁸ was condensed with ethylchloroform-